

FEATURES OF PLAY ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

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ASSOCIATION. General concept of activity. Play, education, work activities and their psychological significance. The social nature, types of work, creativity and inspiration typical of the educational profession. The concept of skills, abilities, habits. **RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CHILDREN'S NEEDS AND INTERESTS**

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Given the great importance of play in the mental development of children, famous educators and thinkers have written down their valuable thoughts on the subject. According to A.I. Makarenko, children's play activities are the only means for them to develop harmoniously physically and mentally. As much as work activities are important for adults, play is just as important for children. "Good play activity," A.I. Makarenko, "seems to be doing well. That is why children behave in the same way in play activities as they grew up." This opinion of A.I. Makarenko expresses a serious consideration of the great opportunity for children to develop high human qualities through play activities. Play activities prepare children for the time of acquiring the social experience of humanity, i.e., educational activities. One cannot suddenly begin to assimilate a social experience. In order to acquire social skills, a person must first have sufficient speech, certain skills, abilities and elementary understanding. And the child achieves this only through play activities.

Play is such a multifaceted activity in children's lives that it combines both the labor and thinking of children and the sources of art, imagination, recreation and joy. All of these processes are reflected in play activities and can provide the full level of life that children need. That's the fascinating part of the game for kids. Play is not only a means of knowing the external environment, things and events, but also a powerful educational tool. In creative and meaningful games, along with all the mental processes of children, their individual qualities are also formed. From this point of view, play is one of the most important preschool educational activities. This means that the success of preschool education depends in many ways on the ability of children to organize their play activities in a purposeful way.

The child's executive playthings (imaginary driving a horse made of sticks, a steamer made of chairs) should not be seen as a departure from reality. The child loves reality, that is, the environment in which he lives and the variety of things and events in it. The child expresses his boundless love for reality and his desire to know the things and events in it in his various play activities. Therefore, the child strives to reflect reality as fully and accurately as possible, creating an imaginary environment in his various varied games.

According to foreign psychologists J. Piaget and Koffka, children live in two different worlds that seem to be separated from each other, namely, the world of fantasies, myths, and the (real) real world. No matter how imaginative children are in their activities, they always look at the real world, the real things in it.

This can be seen in the fact that during the game they evaluate their behavior as "it will happen", "it will not happen". No matter how much they indulge in the game, they will never forget the real world and share it as if it were a model.

Psychologist A.N. According to Leontyev, there is no such thing as a deviation from the reality of children's play activities. The variety of actions and things in children's games are real images of real actions and real things that actually exist in reality. The child is still unable to create imaginary, mythical games that are not related to the real reality in which he lives. Because a child is not yet able to reflect in his play activities what he does not know, see or hear. In order to play this or that game, children must be familiar with life events and many types of work, even if they are elementary. This means that the more meaningful a child's life is and the wider the scope of living, the more diverse his or her games will be. As a result, the child does not get bored. Making children's lives meaningful depends in many ways on education and parents. It is advisable for parents and caregivers to take children on trips from time to time.

Thus, play is not something created by children's imagination, on the contrary, children's imagination itself emerges and develops in the process of play. Children create a variety of imaginative and mythical images in play activities. The process of reflecting things and events in the external environment of man is not a passive process, but an active and creative creative, transformation process.

Another feature of children's play activities is that the game has a general character. In his various games, the child reflects not only the behavior of a

familiar profession, but also the behavior of drivers, police officers, educators, pilots. Of course, young children (sometimes even a small group of children) with very limited life experience and range of activities reflect specific people (mother, father, etc.) and their behavior in their play. In the games of middle and older preschoolers, each image begins to have a common character. Play activities allow children to learn individually. It is convenient to observe the individual characteristics of children, especially through their group games.

In group play, children reflect on the complex life activities of a group of people. For example, in the game "Seller - buyer" children play the role of seller, cashier, worker, buyer. Such group games of children are similar to the activities of actors. This is because in group play, each child strives to perform his or her role well, but also tries not to deviate from the overall content of the game. This requires each child to use all their abilities.

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